

KEY REQUIREMENTS FOR A DIGITAL BANK: CUSTOMER PERSPECTIVE

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Annotation: In this article, you will further enrich your knowledge about digital banking, as this article explains all the principles of digital banking with clear data and graphs. The sections of the article are mainly related to the operating system of modern banks. The study reviewed the work of leading scientists in the field. At the end of the article, the author gave his thoughts and suggestions on the topic.

Keywords: Digital banking, DBF, KYC process, Biometric technologies, market, P2P.

Digital banking is a general term for the development of banking services and the delivery of products through electronic channels such as automated payment machines, telephone, internet, mobile phone. Customers are still waiting for the new fastest banking services, but India is developing technology-based banking services in a revolutionary change, bringing many new features, including very fast response times to banking operations anytime and anywhere. The overall goal of the study is to identify the factors that influence digital banking customer satisfaction. This study also identifies development factors in terms of ease of use, flexibility, affordability, and efficiency of using digital banking services.

The consumer’s view of digital banking is shown in Figure 7.1.

At a minimum, in the retail sector, DBF should offer:

Figure 7.1

Consumer perception of DBF.

1. Integrated and customized experience. The client's cash and, in a broader sense, financial life, including his current account and deposit balances, transactions, outstanding loans, periodic payments, pension contributions and savings, as well as securities accounts. Provide comprehensive, interactive, and intuitive information. Customize your services for different customer segments such as small and informal traders, mass wealthy people, youth market, international travelers or low-income customers. Offer a reliable and relatively inexpensive source of credit for your customers.

2. Digital. Provide a holistic, complete digital experience for customers, including a paperless application and a KYC process. Also provide an interactive and intuitive digital financial planner to streamline customers’ economic lives and optimize their resources: immediate cash flow requirements, savings (including automatic savings), medical expenses, education, retirement (including advanced robo-consultation with services available only to high-level investors) and investment trading instruments, including investments. Give customers the opportunity to apply electronically for a mortgage or loan. Offer competitive insurance contracts for housing, liability, health insurance and travel insurance,

credit verification procedures have been expanded on social media. Submission of reporting documents related to banking activities, including tax reports. Provide access to the Personal Data Warehouse (PDS).

3. First mobile. Enable local mobile electronic payment solutions, including local and international payments and transfers, automatic payments, peer-to-peer (P2P) payments, and money transfers. Instead of thinking of a mobile phone or using it as an additional skill, start with a mobile device and create from there not only a user experience, but also basic infrastructure and credit analysis.

4. Currency services. Provide uninterrupted and affordable foreign exchange services by providing multi-currency accounts, including protection against exchange rate fluctuations. Potentially, a full set of tools to hedge against currency risk, including forward contracts, spot contracts, swaps, and exchange trading options, can be offered.

5. Digital assets. Offer efficient tokenization, handling, storage and storage of digital assets.

6. Biometric technologies. Offer customers biometric technologies such as face and voice biometrics that are actively used at airports and international border controls as a way to access their accounts. Behavioral biometrics currently being developed is a promising way to achieve an additional level of protection.

7. Electronic credit card. Introduce a bank e-credit card with a comprehensive digital wallet and PDS, including pre-defined limits and allowable transactions, consumer-related patterns and at least an electronic ID, an e-card and tools for secure online shopping. View, pay, edit, analyze and archive electronic accounts and generate relevant tax documents.

8. Introduction to the world of P2P. Provide access to “crowd-to-everything,” including P2P payment and lending options.

This study showed that access to digital banking services is based on individuals who are found to be physically healthy in the community. Research is needed to

determine the impact of access to digital banking services among people with disabilities. To have faster processes in digital banking, banks need to invest more in robust and reliable systems to reduce unsuccessful transactions and transaction errors at ATMs, mobile banking and POS-terminals. Banks need to automate most of the services, such as loan repayment and lending, and introduce a queue management system. Banks need to develop software that can be used to improve digital banking that is secure and personal to increase the availability and availability of digital banking operations.

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